

MEDICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF THE LEVELS OF CERTAIN BLOOD PARAMETERS IN INDIVIDUALS WITH TOXOPLASMA VE HERPES INFECTIONS

Abasova D.

*Scientific Research Institute of Medical Preventive named by V.Y. Akhundov,
Head of Department*

Amirova L.

*Scientific Research Institute of Medical Preventive named by V.Y. Akhundov,
Researcher*

Shirnova T.

*Scientific Research Institute of Medical Preventive named by V.Y. Akhundov,
Chief Laboratory Technician*

Gadimli M.

*Scientific Research Institute of Medical Preventive named by V.Y. Akhundov,
Chief Laboratory Technician*

Huseynova G.

*Scientific Research Institute of Medical Preventive named by V.Y. Akhundov,
Chief Laboratory Technician*

Abstract

Blood samples from patients at the V.Y. Akhundov Scientific Research Institute were analyzed. Antibodies were detected using ELISA with "Vester Best" test kits on a Stat Fax 4700 analyzer. Hemogram parameters, including WBC, NEU, LYM, MON, PLT, and HB, were assessed. CRP levels were also measured. The neutrophil-to-lymphocyte (NLR), platelet-to-lymphocyte (PLR), and lymphocyte-to-monocyte (LMR) ratios were calculated. Routine blood tests were used to evaluate hematological parameters, infection severity, and immune response. Patients with toxoplasmosis and HSV1 infections had significantly lower NEU and PLT counts. Infected individuals showed higher LYM counts and elevated CRP levels compared to uninfected individuals. The findings highlight the impact of these infections on hematological markers and immune response.

Keywords: Toxoplasma, herpes, lymphocyte, platelet, CRP, neutrophil.

THE PROBLEM OF OPPORTUNISTIC INFECTIONS

Opportunistic infections are increasingly becoming a significant issue in modern times. This is due to several factors that weaken the immune system, including the rising number of individuals undergoing immunosuppressive treatments for chronic diseases, the increasing prevalence of HIV-infected individuals, and the development of effective but aggressive treatments for cancer. Additionally, many people are asymptomatic carriers of these pathogens. Approximately 90% of the population is infected with Herpes Simplex Virus (HSV) types 1 and 2, while around 30% are infected with toxoplasmosis. Given their clinical polymorphism and the absence of specific symptoms, the diagnosis and treatment of opportunistic diseases represent a serious multidisciplinary challenge.

Opportunistic infections are caused by a wide range of microorganisms, including bacteria, fungi, parasites, and viruses. In most cases, these microorganisms cause asymptomatic infections in healthy individuals. However, when the immune system is weakened, they can lead to life-threatening infections [1,2]. These infections are triggered by immunodeficiency of any etiology and tend to follow a chronic course, with periodic flare-ups and damage to vital organs. Opportunistic infections are characterized by the spread of microorganisms through the lymphatic and hematogenous pathways, leading to the formation of ectopic foci. Opportunistic infections (OIs) are defined as infections

caused by bacteria, fungi, viruses, or parasites that normally do not cause disease but become pathogenic when the body's immune defenses are compromised [1]. These infections may manifest as unusually severe infections caused by common pathogens. In all cases, opportunistic infections take advantage of a weakened immune system or altered microbiota in the host [2].

Due to various environmental factors, particularly in the case of mycobacteria, fungi, and parasites, OIs exhibit significant geographical variability [3,4]. Platelets are among the most common blood components, and their role in both innate and adaptive immune responses to various types of infections has been studied [10]. In opportunistic infections, platelets have been found to interact with neutrophils, monocytes, and dendritic cells, indicating their involvement in immune system interactions. Unlike platelet or lymphocyte counts, the platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio is considered a more valuable marker for predicting different types of inflammation. Other immune cells, such as lymphocytes and monocytes, also play a crucial role in the immune response against opportunistic infections [5,6].

Studies have shown that individuals with HIV/AIDS have a reduced ability of B cells to produce antibodies against opportunistic pathogens. Additionally, research has demonstrated that in individuals infected with HIV/AIDS, monocytes exhibit a diminished ability to engulf and eliminate opportunistic pathogens [7,8].

Thus, studying the immunological changes associated with opportunistic infections is essential for improving their diagnosis, treatment, and prevention.

OBJECTIVE AND TASKS OF THE STUDY

The objective of this study was to investigate the changes occurring in the immune system of individuals infected with opportunistic infections.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were carried out:

- Determination of the levels of M and G immunoglobulins in individuals with opportunistic infections.
- Investigation of changes in certain blood parameters in cases of herpes and toxoplasmosis, which are among opportunistic infections.

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF THE STUDY

For this study, blood samples were collected from patients who visited the clinical laboratory of the V.Y. Akhundov Scientific Research Institute of Medical Prevention. A total of 306 individuals participated in the study. Among them, 76 individuals tested seropositive for herpes, 77 for toxoplasmosis, 36 for cytomegalovirus, and 55 for mixed infections. Blood samples from seronegative individuals were used as a control group. No seropositivity for IgM was observed among the examined individuals.

The presence of antibodies in individuals infected with opportunistic infections was determined using the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) method, employing test kits produced by the "Vester Best" company. The tests were performed using the Stat Fax 4700 semi-automatic analyzer.

The absolute and relative counts of lymphocytes and leukocytes in the blood were evaluated based on hemogram parameters. The counts of white blood cells (WBC), neutrophils (NEU), lymphocytes (LYM), monocytes (MON), platelets (PLT), and hemoglobin (HB) were recorded. The C-reactive protein (CRP) levels in infected individuals were also assessed.

Additionally, the following hematological indices were calculated:

- Neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR): calculated by dividing the absolute neutrophil count by the absolute lymphocyte count.

- Platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio (PLR): calculated by dividing the absolute platelet count by the absolute lymphocyte count.

- Lymphocyte-to-monocyte ratio (LMR): calculated by dividing the absolute lymphocyte count by the absolute monocyte count in routine blood tests.

OBTAINED RESULTS

The study was conducted in the following directions:

- The seropositivity of individuals infected with opportunistic infections was examined using the ELISA method.

- Changes in certain blood parameters (including leukocytes, lymphocytes, neutrophils, platelets, etc.) and C-reactive protein (CRP) levels in peripheral blood were analyzed during these infections.

A comparative analysis of blood parameters was conducted between individuals with and without herpes infection.

- The average WBC (white blood cell) value in the herpes group was higher than in the control group (10.95 vs. 9.77, both in $10^9/L$).

- The LYM (lymphocyte) value was also significantly higher in the herpes group (6.05±3.03) compared to the control group (5.1±1.53, $p<0.0001$).

- The average NEU (neutrophil) value (2.30 vs. 2.79, both in $10^9/L$) and PLT (platelet) count (324.35 vs. 380.93, both in $10^9/L$) were lower in the herpes group compared to the control group.

- Similarly, HB (hemoglobin) levels were lower in the herpes group (11.40 vs. 12.00 g/dL).

The values of NLR (neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio), PLR (platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio), and LMR (lymphocyte-to-monocyte ratio) in the HSV infection group were significantly different from those in the control group (all $p<0.0001$). These ratios serve as important indicators of the intensity and immune response analysis during infection.

In addition, the mean CRP (C-reactive protein) level in the herpes infection group (29.6±19.2) was higher than in the control group (25±0.15, $p=0.001$) (Table 1).

Table 1

Hematological Parameters of Individuals with Herpes Infection and the Control Group

Routine Blood Test	HERPES infection ($n=76$)	Control Group ($n=76$)	p-value
WBC ($10^9/L$)	10,95±4,38	9,77±3,18	0,003
NEU ($10^9/L$)	2,30±1,78	2,79±1,61	0,005
LYM ($10^9/L$)	6,05±3,03	5,1±1,53	<0,0001
MON ($10^9/L$)	1,31±0,63	1,27±0,56	0,483
PLT ($10^9/L$)	324,35±125,49	380,93±119,35	<0,0001
HB (g/dl)	11,40±2,17	12,00± 2,22	0,009
NLR	0,37±0,31	0,56±0,34	<0,0001
PLR	54,69±29,57	79,03±34,68	<0,0001
LMR	5,98±2,85	4,79±2,91	<0,0001
CRP	29,6±19,2	22,3±0,15	<0,001

A comparative analysis of routine blood test results was conducted between individuals with and without Toxoplasma infection.

- The average WBC (white blood cell) value was higher in the Toxoplasma group than in the control group (9.95 vs. 8.98, both in $10^9/L$).

- The LYM (lymphocyte) value was significantly higher in the Toxoplasma group (6.92±3.09) compared to the control group (5.27±1.72, p<0.0001).
- The NEU (neutrophil) count was lower in the Toxoplasma group compared to the control group (2.45 vs. 2.89, both in 10⁹/L), suggesting that Toxoplasma infection may contribute to a decrease in neutrophil cells.
- The PLT (platelet) count was lower in the Toxoplasma group (354.89 vs. 380.93, both in 10⁹/L), indicating a potential reduction in platelet levels due to Toxoplasma infection.

- The average HB (hemoglobin) value was also slightly lower in the Toxoplasma group (11.79 vs. 11.90 g/dL).
- The NLR (neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio), PLR (platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio), and LMR (lymphocyte-to-monocyte ratio) values showed significant differences between the Toxoplasma infection group and the control group.
- The mean CRP (C-reactive protein) level in the Toxoplasma group (32.4±16.1) was higher than in the control group (25±0.3, p=0.001) (Table 2).

Table 2

Hematological Parameters of the Toxoplasma Infection Group and the Control Group

Routine Blood Test	Toxoplasmosis Infection (n = 77)	Control Group (n =77)	p-value
WBC (10 ⁹ /L)	9,95±4,38	8,98±3,18	0.003
NEU (10 ⁹ /L)	2.45±1.78	2,89±1,61	0.005
LYM (10 ⁹ /L)	6,92±3,09	5,27±1,72	<0,0001
MON (10 ⁹ /L)	1,51±0,63	1,57±0,56	0.483
PLT (10 ⁹ /L)	354,89±125,49	380,93±119,35	<0,0001
HB (g/dl)	11.79±2.17	11,90±2,22	0.009
NLR	0,47±0,31	0,65±0,34	<0,0001
PLR	61,34±29,57	81,03±34,68	<0,0001
LMR	6,01±2,85	5,09±2,91	<0,0001
CRP	32,4±16,1	25,2±0,3	<0,001

DISCUSSION

• The conducted studies have revealed that individuals with herpes and toxoplasmosis infections have significantly lower NEU, NLR, and PLR levels compared to those without these infections. However, patients with these infections exhibit higher WBC and LYM counts, as well as relatively elevated levels of C-reactive protein.

• It is known that congenital herpes infection is widespread in China, with herpes seroprevalence reported to be over 90%. The rate of congenital HSV infection among all live births is approximately 0.7%. Herpes can affect multiple organs with various manifestations, including microcephaly, brain damage, hearing impairment, retinitis, and hepatosplenomegaly. It has also been associated with myelosuppression, including granulocytopenia, thrombocytopenia, and anemia [7, 8].

• Platelets are among the most common blood components. Their role in both innate and adaptive immune responses across various types of infections has been studied [9, 10]. In opportunistic infections, platelets have been found to interact with neutrophils, monocytes, and dendritic cells, indicating their involvement in immune system interactions. Unlike the individual counts of platelets or lymphocytes, the platelet-lymphocyte ratio (PLR) serves as a more valuable marker for predicting different inflammatory conditions [11, 12]. As a novel inflammatory marker, PLR has been associated with tumors, coronary heart disease, and connective tissue diseases.

Scientific Novelty and Practical Significance

• The obtained results not only provide an assessment of certain hematological changes during op-

portunistic infections but also contribute to the diagnosis of these infections, identification of their risk factors, and improvement of treatment and prevention methods.

CONCLUSIONS

• The study demonstrated that opportunistic infections have a significant impact on determining the immunological and serological status of individuals and that these infections may independently influence immunoglobulin C levels.

• The research analyzed specific changes in blood parameters associated with Toxoplasma and HSV1 infections, evaluating hematological parameters, infection severity, and their effects.

• It was found that individuals with Toxoplasma and HSV1 infections had significantly lower neutrophil and platelet counts compared to those without these infections, while lymphocyte counts and C-reactive protein (CRP) levels were notably higher.

References

1. Jafari, Mohammad Mahdi, et al. "Immune system roles in pathogenesis, prognosis, control, and treatment of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection." *International Immunopharmacology* 124 (2023): 110872.
2. Robben, Paul M., et al. "Recruitment of Gr-1+ monocytes is essential for control of acute toxoplasmosis." *The Journal of Experimental Medicine* 201.11 (2005): 1761-1769.
3. Biswas, Aindrila, et al. "Ly6Chigh monocytes control cerebral toxoplasmosis." *The Journal of Immunology* 194.7 (2015): 3223-3235.
4. Dobbs, Katherine R., Juliet N. Crabtree, and Arlene E. Dent. "Innate immunity to malaria—the role of monocytes." *Immunological Reviews* 293.1 (2020): 8-24.

5. Benevides, Luciana, et al. "CCR2 receptor is essential to activate microbicidal mechanisms to control *Toxoplasma gondii* infection in the central nervous system." *The American Journal of Pathology* 173.3 (2008): 741-751.
6. Dai, Xu-Ming, et al. "Targeted disruption of the mouse colony-stimulating factor 1 receptor gene results in osteopetrosis, mononuclear phagocyte deficiency, increased primitive progenitor cell frequencies, and reproductive defects." *Blood, The Journal of the American Society of Hematology* 99.1 (2002): 111-120.
7. Wong, Kok Loon, et al. "Gene expression profiling reveals the defining features of the classical, intermediate, and nonclassical human monocyte subsets." *Blood, The Journal of the American Society of Hematology* 118.5 (2011): e16-e31.
8. Zigmond, Ehud, et al. "Ly6Chi monocytes in the inflamed colon give rise to proinflammatory effector cells and migratory antigen-presenting cells." *Immunity* 37.6 (2012): 1076-1090.
9. Boettcher, Steffen, and Markus G. Manz. "Regulation of inflammation- and infection-driven hematopoiesis." *Trends in Immunology* 38.5 (2017): 345-357.
10. Bhadra, Rajarshi, Jason P. Gigley, and Imtiaz A. Khan. "PD-1-mediated attrition of polyfunctional memory CD8+ T cells in chronic *Toxoplasma* infection." *The Journal of Infectious Diseases* 206.1 (2012): 125-134.
11. Sasai, Miwa, and Masahiro Yamamoto. "Pathogen recognition receptors: ligands and signaling pathways by Toll-like receptors." *International Reviews of Immunology* 32.2 (2013): 116-133.
12. Merah-Mourah, F., et al. "Identification of novel human monocyte subsets and evidence for phenotypic groups defined by interindividual variations of expression of adhesion molecules." *Scientific Reports* 10.1 (2020): 4397.